

Graphical abstract

Bioactive-rich
SUPRAS extract

Highlights

- SUPRAS are applied for first time for valorization of food waste (spent coffee grounds)
- Bioactive compounds were extracted in an good rate for industrial applications
- SUPRAS extracts showed high polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity
- SUPRAS extracts exhibited antimicrobial activity (gram-negative bacteria)

29 **Abstract**

30

31 In this study, we assess the potential of supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS) for valorization of
32 spent coffee grounds (SCG). SUPRAS, made up of self-assembled amphiphilic aggregates
33 dispersed in an aqueous or hydro-organic medium, are excellent extractants that provide multiple
34 binding interactions (hydrogen bonds, dispersion, dipole-dipole, etc.) and microenvironments of
35 different polarity due to their special internal architecture. In this work, SUPRAS made up of
36 different amphiphiles (decanoic acid and hexanol) and hydro-organic media (water-ethanol and
37 water-tetrahydrofuran) were investigated for extraction of bioactives from SCG. Extraction was
38 optimized from the yield obtained for caffeine and 5-chlorogenic acid, that were considered as
39 model compounds. Under optimal extraction conditions, the profile of bioactive compounds in
40 the extracts was screened by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry and the total
41 phenolic content was estimated. The antioxidants and antimicrobial properties of the extracts
42 were also evaluated. Bioactive compounds were extracted from wet SCG up to 3.32 mg.g⁻¹ and
43 4.3 mg.g⁻¹ SCG of caffeine and chlorogenic acid, respectively. Extracts showed antioxidant
44 capacity by different assays (DPPH, TEAC, FRAP) in accordance with their high total phenolic
45 content (60.1 mg CGA per mg of extracted dry SCG). SUPRAS offered advantages in terms of
46 rapidity (extraction for 1 min) and simplicity (the process involved stirring and centrifugation at
47 room temperature), thus avoiding costly processes based on high pressure and temperature.
48 Furthermore, SUPRAS extracts exhibited certain degree of antimicrobial effects against, *S.*
49 *aureus* and *B. cereus* and a high effect against *S. enterica* and *P. putida*.

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51 **Keywords:** supramolecular solvents; spent coffee grounds; bioactive compounds; valorization

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60 1. Introduction

61
62 The agricultural world production is continuously increasing as a result of the rising global
63 demand for food and generates billion tons of by-products each year [1]. There is a growing
64 interest in the recovery of bioactive compounds from agro-waste for application in functional
65 foods and nutraceutical formulations [2]. The coffee industry alone generates about 2 billion tons
66 of agro-waste, which represent a great pollution hazard [3]. Coffee pulp, husks, silverskin, peel
67 and spend coffee grounds are common coffee by-products [4] and have been reported of interest
68 as substrates for mushroom cultivation [5], immobilization of enzymes [6], production of
69 bioethanol [7] composting [8], and extraction of bioactive compounds [9–11].

70
71 Spent coffee grounds (SCG), a high humidity residue (up to ~80%) obtained in coffee beverage
72 preparation and instant coffee manufacturing, is the most abundant coffee by-product (45-50%)
73 [12,13]. SCG is produced at a rate of 6 million tons a year [12]. Valorization of coffee by-
74 products through the recovery of bioactives, particularly alkaloids and polyphenols, has
75 increasingly become of interest for food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries [13–16]. The
76 major alkaloid in coffee by-products is caffeine, which shows anti-inflammatory and
77 immunosuppressant effects [16]. Regarding polyphenols, they include a broad range of
78 compounds including tannins, flavanols, flavones, anthocyanins, proanthocyanidins, and
79 phenolic, hydroxybenzoic and hydroxycinnamic acids [17]. Polyphenols have demonstrated
80 antioxidant, anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory and anti-carcinogenic activities [13–15].

81
82 Extraction of bioactives from SCG has been investigated using different solvents and techniques,
83 including conventional solid-liquid extraction (SLE) [18,19], supercritical fluid extraction (SFE),
84 with and without co-solvent [20], Soxhlet extraction [20], and ultrasound (USAE) [20–22] or
85 microwave (MAE) [21,23] assisted extraction. Extraction efficiencies, usually given as total
86 phenolic compounds (TPC) and expressed as gallic acid (GAE) or chlorogenic acid (CAE)
87 equivalents [24], are highly dependent on the type of solvent, the solvent/solid ratio, the number
88 of extraction steps and the extraction time and temperature, among others factors [15].
89 Extractions have been carried out using polar (e.g. methanol and ethanol) and medium or non-
90 polar (e.g. dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, hexane) solvents [18–20,23], supercritical fluids [20],

91 subcritical water [21], and deep eutectic solvents [22]. Common conditions for conventional SLE
92 include solvent/solid ratios of around 30-40 mL/g SCG, extraction temperatures in the range 50-
93 65 °C and extraction times for 1-2 h, which give extraction efficiencies for TPCs of about 16-18
94 mg GAE/g SCG [18–20]. Extraction efficiencies for TPCs in SFE increase in the presence of
95 ethanol as co-solvent (e.g. around 42 mg CAE per gram of extract using 8% ethanol, which is
96 equivalent to ~4 mg CAE/g SCG taking into account yields of about 10%) [20]. Extraction of
97 phenolic compounds have been also reported for energy-assisted techniques, namely Soxhlet
98 extraction [20], USAE [20] or MAE [23]. Thus, TPCs were in the range 119-167 mg CAE/g
99 extract (18-22 mg CAE/g SCG; extraction yields 12-15%) with Soxhlet extraction using solvents
100 of different polarity, solvent /solid ratios of 30, and 6 h of extraction at the boiling temperature of
101 the solvent [20]. Likewise, the application of USAE for 2 h, at room temperature and
102 solvent/solid ratios of 30, permitted to achieve extraction efficiencies for TPCs in the range of
103 221-588 mg CAE/g extract (21.9-71.7 mg CAE/g SCG; extraction yields 10-12%) [20].
104 Application of MAE was also assessed; it provided up to 399 mg GAE/g extract (21.5 mg/g
105 SCG; extraction yield 5.4) with 40 s of irradiation and a solvent/solid ratio of 9 [23]. All these
106 figures indicate that SCG is a valuable source for bioactives and that further research should be
107 intended to reduce extraction efforts in order to make their valorization simpler and more cost-
108 effective.

109
110 In this paper, we propose for the first time the use of supramolecular solvents (SUPRASs) for the
111 extraction of bioactives from SCG. SUPRASs are nanostructured liquids spontaneously
112 produced in colloidal suspensions of amphiphiles through a bottom-up approach based on
113 sequential self-assembly phenomena [25,26]. The synthesis is made by a simple two-step
114 process. First, amphiphiles spontaneously assemble into three-dimensional individual aggregates
115 (mainly micelles and/or vesicles). The second stage generates a new highly packed phase by the
116 assembly of the aggregates into a nano or microstructured liquid (SUPRAS phase). This second
117 phase is triggered by an external stimuli such pH or temperature changes, addition of salt or
118 addition of a poor solvent for the amphiphile, which diminishes the repulsion among the
119 aggregates and promotes their assembly [25]. The SUPRAS phase remains in equilibrium with
120 the bulk solution, which contains the amphiphile at the critical aggregation concentration.
121 SUPRAS can be collected and stored if required (keeping its structure and properties) for

122 application to solid samples or applied together with the equilibrium solution, which acts as a
123 wetting and dispersion phase for the matrix [27].

124

125 The capability of SUPRASs for developing efficient processes for extraction of bioactives is
126 based on the presence of different polarity microenvironments into their ordered structures, the
127 high concentration of amphiphiles make up them (up to 1 mg/ μ L), and the possibility of
128 producing tailored SUPRASs by selection of the amphiphile or the environment for self-
129 assembly [28]. Thus, SUPRASs are able to efficiently extract compounds spanning a wide
130 polarity range using low solvent/solid ratios [27]. On the other hand, SUPRASs with restricted
131 access properties (SUPRAS-RAM) have been reported that permit the extraction of low
132 molecular weight compounds while excluding macromolecules [29]. These properties have
133 allowed the development of innovative strategies for sample preparation in the determination of
134 organic contaminants and metals in food, the environment and biological fluids [25,26]. More
135 recently, SUPRASs have also proved promising for the extraction of bioactives from microalgae
136 [30] and the removal of contaminants in wastewater [31].

137

138 The suitability of SUPRASs for the extraction of bioactives from SCG obtained by the drip filter
139 method was here explored. For this purpose, two types of SUPRASs, synthesized from decanoic
140 acid [32] and hexanol [33] in hydro-organic media (water and ethanol or tetrahydrofuran) were
141 investigated. Extraction efficiencies were evaluated by monitoring caffeine and chlorogenic acid,
142 two major representatives of alkaloids and polyphenols, respectively. Under the optimized
143 conditions, the SUPRAS extracts were further analysed to identify the main bioactives, to
144 estimate their total phenolic content and evaluate their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.
145 Below, the more relevant results are presented and discussed.

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151 **1. Materials and methods**

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153 *1.1 Chemicals*

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155 Caffeine (1,3,7-trimethylxantine, HPLC grade), 5-chlorogenic acid (5-O-Caffeoylquinic acid, 5-
156 CGA, 98%), (±)-6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethyl-chroman-2-carboxylic acid (98,1%, Trolox),
157 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS), 2,2 diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl
158 (DPPH), decanoic acid (98%), ethanol (HPLC grade), methanol (99,9%), 2,3,5-
159 triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC), glacial acetic acid and tetrahydrofuran (HPLC grade) were
160 purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, USA). 1-hexanol (98%), hydrochloric acid
161 (37%), and 2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (TPTZ) were supplied by Merck (Darmstadt,
162 Germany). Potassium persulfate was purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain), ferric chloride
163 from Carlo Erba (Val-de-Reuil, France) and potassium acetate (99,4%) from JT Baker (Madrid,
164 Spain). All chemicals were analytical reagent-grade and were used as supplied. Pure water was
165 prepared using a Milli-Q, Ultrapure water purification system equipped with a 0.22- μ m filter
166 (MA, USA).

167

168 Three reagents were prepared for evaluation of the antioxidant capacity of SUPRAS extracts
169 containing coffee bioactives. The DPPH reagent was freshly prepared by dissolving 1 mg of
170 DPPH in 50 mL of methanol and diluted with methanol to give an absorbance of 1.057 ± 0.005 at
171 529 nm. It was kept in the dark at room temperature when not used. The ABTS⁺ radical reagent
172 was freshly prepared by dissolving 97 mg of ABTS and 16.5 mg of potassium persulfate in 25
173 mL of distilled water and keeping the solution for 16 hours under dark. Then, it was diluted with
174 ethanol to yield an absorbance of 0.635 ± 0.005 at 732 nm. The reagent FRAP (ferric reducing
175 antioxidant power) was prepared by the mixing of three solutions in a thermostatic bath at 35 °C;
176 250 mL of acetic acid/acetate buffer (40 mM, pH 3.6), 2.5 mL of an aqueous solution of ferric
177 chloride (20 mM) and 2.5 mL of TPTZ (10 mM) in 40 mM HCl. The absorbance of the reagent
178 solution was 0.107 ± 0.005 at 595 nm.

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182 *1.2 Apparatus*

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184 A high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) coupled to a UV Detector (Shimadzu, Japan)
185 was employed for the quantification of caffeine and 5-CGA. The stationary phase was an Ultra
186 C₈ column (5 µm particle size, 150 mm length, 4.6 mm i.d.) from Restek (France). All data were
187 acquired and processed using the LabSolutions Software (Shimadzu, Japan). For the target
188 screening of bioactive compounds in SUPRAS extracts under optimal conditions (section 2.5)
189 we performed LC-MS/MS analysis. The equipment consisted in an Agilent Technologies 1200
190 LC system with a column ACE 3 C18-PFP column (3 mm i.d., 150 mm length, 3.0 µm particle
191 size) preceded by a precolumn Phenomenex KJ 0-4282 Security Guard Cartridge Kit, Ea. The
192 detector was an Agilent Technologies 6420 Triple Quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with
193 an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in negative and positive modes. Raw data were
194 controlled and processed using Agilent MassHunter Software® (version B.07.00). Other
195 instrumentation used for sample preparation were a vortex-shaker REAX Top (Heidolph,
196 Schwabach, Germany) and a 12 x 1.5 – 2 mL angle rotor Minicen centrifuge from Ortoalresa
197 (Madrid, Spain). Optimization of the extraction of coffee byproducts was carried out in 2 mL-
198 microtubes Safe-Lock from Eppendorf Iberica (Madrid, Spain). A vortex shaker from Vortorex
199 (Heathrow Scientific, Vernon Hills, IL, USA) with an attachment for 4 tubes, and a high-speed
200 brushless centrifuge BX 24 (Unico, USA) were used for sample preparation. Antimicrobial
201 activity was evaluated in a laminar flow cabinet Physis (AirFlux, Malaysia).

202 203 *1.3 Spent coffee grounds*

204
205 Spent coffee grounds (SCG) were obtained from a drip filter brewing method consisting in
206 flowing water at 92–96 °C through a ground coffee bed so that the extract drips from the brewing
207 chamber into the pot. The coffee used in all the experiments was the variety Castillo produced in
208 Circasia (Colombia). The water content in the SCG was 74.0±0.8%. SCG samples were not
209 dried and immediately processed or stored at -18 °C.

2.4. SUPRAS production

SUPRASs of different composition were produced by adding ultrapure water to a colloidal suspension of decanoic acid or hexanol in THF or ethanol (total volume of the mixture: 2 mL). Under addition of water, the decanoic acid or hexanol aggregates in the colloidal suspension gave spontaneously oily droplets that associated as clusters and finally separated from the bulk solution as a new liquid phase named SUPRAS. The whole solution, containing both the SUPRAS (at the top) and the hydro-organic equilibrium solution, was added to the SCG. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the general procedure followed for SUPRAS production.

2.5. SUPRAS-based extraction of bioactives from SCG

The following variables were considered for the optimization of SUPRAS-based extraction of bioactives from SCG: (a) type of organic solvent used to produce the colloidal suspension (ethanol or THF); (b) type of amphiphile (decanoic acid or hexanol) making up the SUPRAS; (c) amphiphile concentration in the SUPRAS synthetic solution (8, 16 and 24 % v/v), and (d) organic solvent concentration in the SUPRAS synthetic solution (20, 30 and 40 % v/v). The extraction of bioactives was performed by adding 0.35 g of wet SCG to the SUPRAS synthetic solution (see section 2.4) in polypropylene centrifuge microtubes. The composition of the SUPRAS synthetic solution was varied as follows: hexanol or decanoic acid (66-574 μL), ethanol or THF (176-1024 μL) and distilled water (656-1560 μL). The sample size was kept constant at 0.35 g to ensure good sample dispersibility at the SUPRAS volume/sample size ratio that was set for the laboratory scale. The mixtures were vortex-shaken for 1 min at 3,000 rpm for the extraction of bioactives and then centrifuged for 20 minutes at 4,519 g to accelerate the separation of SUPRAS from the bulk equilibrium phase (in the middle) and precipitate (at the bottom). The volume of SUPRAS was measured using a digital caliper [33]. The volume of SUPRAS produced varies under different synthetic conditions (usually increasing with the concentration of both the amphiphile and the organic solvent) and consequently this affects concentration factors (ratio of SUPRAS volume/sample size). SUPRAS volumes varied in the range 61 – 1476 μL under the tested conditions. Experiments were done in triplicate. Figure 1 shows a schematic picture of the SUPRAS extraction procedure.

245
246 The final optimal SUPRAS synthesis conditions were 24% v/v hexanol and 30% v/v ethanol.
247 The average SUPRAS volume was 980 ± 10 μL (2.8 mL SUPRAS/g wet SCG). These conditions
248 were finally tested for identification of bioactives, estimation of the total phenolic content and
249 antioxidant and antimicrobial activity

250

251 *2.6. Analysis of caffeine and chlorogenic acid by HPLC-UV*

252

253 Caffeine and 5-CGA acid contents in the SUPRAS extracts were determined by HPLC-UV. The
254 detector wavelength was set at 254 nm. The mobile phase consisted of 69.9% v/v of water, 30%
255 v/v of methanol and 0.1% v/v of acetic in isocratic mode. The flow rate was set at 0.6 mL min^{-1}
256 and the sample injection volume was $20 \mu\text{L}$. Quantitative analysis was conducted by external
257 calibration using standard solutions of caffeine and 5-CGA prepared in ultrapure water in the
258 concentration range of $5 - 100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

259

260 *2.7. Profile of bioactive compounds in SUPRAS extracts by HPLC-MS/MS and estimation of* 261 *total phenolic content*

262

263 The presence of the main bioactives compounds present in SUPRAS extracts under optimal
264 conditions (section 2.5.) was confirmed by target screening with LC-MS/MS experiments. The
265 mobile phase was made up of Milli-Q water with 0.1% acetic acid (A) and MeOH:Acetonitrile
266 50:50 v/v (B) at a flow rate of $0.3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. The injection volume was $5 \mu\text{L}$. The gradient was
267 as follow: initial 5% B hold for 0.1 min, linear gradient to 30% B in 25 min and to 40% B in the
268 next 10 min. Finally, B was increased to 100% at 35.1 min and maintained for 10 min to remove
269 possible hydrophobic compounds form the column. The column was re-conditioned for 10 min
270 before injection. The MRM transitions for target masses of the bioactives identified in SUPRAS
271 extracts are given in Table 1. The MS parameters were: fragmentor 100 V, collision energy 15
272 eV, cell accelerator voltage 4 V, dwell 20 ms. Source parameters were: gas temperature, 350°C ;
273 gas flow, $12 \text{ L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$; nebulizer gas pressure, 30 psi; capillary voltage, -4000 V. Total phenolic
274 content was estimated from the sum of chromatographic peaks of the identified phenolic
275 compounds with external calibration against 5-CGA, due to the lack of authentic standards for all
276 of them.

277 2.8. Antioxidant activity assays
278

279 The antioxidant activity of the SUPRAS extracts obtained under the optimal conditions specified
280 in section 2.5 was evaluated by the DPPH, TEAC [34] and FRAP [35] methods. Control assays
281 with Trolox were run in parallel for TEAC. The decrease of the absorbance of the reagent
282 solutions, measured as inhibition, was calculated from the following equation [34]:
283

$$\%inhibition = \frac{Abs_0 - Abs_{30}}{Abs_0} * 100$$

284
285 where Abs_0 is the absorbance of DPPH, ABTS⁺ or FRAP reagent solution at time zero and Abs_{30}
286 is the absorbance of the reagent in the presence of the bioactive coffee compounds at 30 minutes
287 of reaction (as mentioned below).
288

289 2.8.1. DPPH radical scavenging assay
290

291 Aliquots of 100 μ L of SUPRAS (previously diluted in 1:10 with methanol) or methanol as blank
292 were mixed with 2 mL of DPPH solution. The mixture was vortexed for a minute and placed in
293 the dark for 30 min. Finally, the absorbance of the mixture was measured at 529 nm. The final
294 concentration of extract tested was ~4.1 mg SUPRAS extract /mL.
295

296 2.8.2. Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) assay
297

298 The assays were made by mixing 50 μ L of methanol as blank or SUPRAS extracts (previously
299 diluted in 1:10 with methanol) and 1450 μ L of the free radical ABTS⁺ stock solution prepared as
300 indicated in section 2.1. The mixture was vortexed for a minute and placed in the dark for 30
301 min. The absorbance was measured at 732 nm and the percentage of inhibition was referred to
302 TEAC. The final concentration of extract tested was 2.7 mg SUPRAS extract/mL.
303

304 2.8.3. Ferric reducing antioxidant potential (FRAP) assay
305

306 Aliquots of 30 μ L of SUPRAS extracts (previously diluted in 1:10 with methanol) or methanol
307 as blank, 90 μ L of water and 900 μ L of the FRAP reagent were mixed and incubated during 30

308 minutes at 37 °C. The absorbance was measured at 595 nm. The final concentration of extract
309 tested was 2.5 mg SUPRAS extract/mL.

310

311 *2.9. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing method*

312

313 The colorimetric broth microdilution method with 2,3-diphenyl-5-thienyl-(2)-tetrazolium
314 chloride (TTC) [36,37] was used to determine the lowest concentration of the assayed
315 antimicrobial agent (minimal inhibitory concentration, MIC). Suspensions of *S. enterica* (ATCC
316 0363), *S. aureus* (ATCC 0496), *P. putida* (ATCC 49128) and *B. cereus* (ATCC 14579) were
317 growth at 37°C in Tryptic Soy broth (TSB) until a concentration of 10⁶ colonies forming units
318 (cfu)/mL was reached. Initially, 100 µL of TSB with 1% of TTC (indicator of metabolic activity)
319 were added in each well of a sterile 96-well microplate followed by 100 µL of SUPRAS extracts
320 (undiluted and diluted at 1:10 and 1:100 with distilled water). Finally, 100 µL of the previously
321 standardized microorganisms were inoculated. Final extract concentrations were 287, 28.7 and
322 2.87 mg SUPRAS extract/mL. After incubating for 24 hours, a color change in the wells was
323 observed and those showing microbial growth were pink-colored.

324

325 **3. Results and discussion**

326

327 *3.1. SUPRAS-based extraction of bioactives from SCG*

328

329 The ability of SUPRASs to develop efficient and cost-effective processes for extraction of
330 bioactives from SCG was evaluated by monitoring the extraction yield for caffeine and
331 chlorogenic acid (5-CGA), which were selected as model compounds for alkaloids and
332 polyphenols, respectively. These compounds can establish donor and/or acceptor hydrogen
333 bonds, and polar and dispersion interactions, so the components making up the SUPRAS were
334 selected to maximize these types of interactions.

335

336 Two amphiphiles (decanoic acid and hexanol) and two hydro-organic media (THF:water and
337 ethanol:water) were chosen for SUPRAS production. Both, carboxylic acids [32] and alkanols
338 [29] have been reported to give SUPRASs made up of inverted hexagonal aggregates where the

339 polar groups surround aqueous cavities and the hydrocarbon chains disperse in the organic
340 solvent (see schematic in Figure 1). The amphiphile functional groups (-OH, -COOH) provide
341 hydrogen bonds and polar interactions, while the alkyl chains give dispersion interactions, so
342 both alkaloids and polyphenols can be solubilized in the hexagonal nanostructures of the
343 SUPRAS by mixed mode mechanisms, which should enhance extraction. On the other hand,
344 ethanol and THF, used to produce the colloidal suspension of the amphiphile, were selected on
345 the basis of their different polarity, which should also influence the extraction of the target
346 compounds.

347
348 Optimization of the SUPRAS-based extraction was carried out according to the procedure
349 specified in section 2.5. The SCG obtained by the drip filter method were subjected to extraction
350 as collected (viz. without drying the by-product) in order to reduce costs and speed up the
351 valorization process. Although bioactives in the SCG were solubilized in the SUPRAS, the
352 equilibrium solution generated in SUPRAS formation (see Figure 1) was also used in the
353 extraction process with the aim of facilitating both the dispersion of the SCG and the SUPRAS
354 extract overflows.

355
356 Figures 2 and 3 show the average extraction recoveries obtained for caffeine and 5-CGA,
357 respectively, when the SCG were subjected to extraction with each of the SUPRAS investigated.
358 Results are expressed as mg of bioactive per g of dry SCG in order to facilitate comparison with
359 previous reported procedures. Each SUPRAS was produced at different proportions (expressed
360 as volume percentages) of the ternary mixture (viz. amphiphile:organic solvent:water), which
361 permitted to vary both SUPRAS composition and volume [29,32]. Thus, increased volume of
362 SUPRAS was obtained by increasing the concentration of the amphiphile at constant organic
363 solvent/water volume ratios in the synthesis. On the other hand, increased volume of SUPRAS
364 was obtained by increasing the organic solvent/water volume ratios in the synthesis at constant
365 amphiphile concentration.

366
367 According to the results (Fig. 2 and 3), hexanol was better extractant for both caffeine and 5-
368 CGA than decanoic acid. The stronger hydrogen bonding ability of hexanol over decanoic acid
369 (which is related to its shorter alkyl chain length) could explain this behavior. In general,

370 recoveries for both bioactives increased or kept constant as a function of amphiphile
371 concentration, at least in the range 8-24%, due to the increase of available binding interactions.
372 Regarding the organic solvent, maximal extraction yields were usually obtained for 40% of THF
373 and 30% of ethanol, being the recovery slightly greater for ethanol. Since, in addition, this
374 solvent is more biocompatible and authorized for use in author industry, ethanol was selected for
375 the production of the colloidal suspension of hexanol. Hexanol is also an authorized food
376 additive by FDA and EU (flavouring substance).

377
378 The maximum extraction rates of caffeine and of CGA (expressed both in dry weight) were 3.32
379 ± 0.07 mg g⁻¹ and 4.3 ± 0.1 mg g⁻¹, respectively, by extraction of the SCG with a SUPRAS
380 obtained from 24% v/v hexanol, 30% v/v ethanol and 46% v/v water. These extracts were
381 selected as optimal for further characterization of functional properties.

382
383 The contents of caffeine and 5-CGA in SCG have been reported to be highly dependent on the
384 extraction process and the SCG source [13, 38,39]. Caffeine and 5-CGA contents were
385 previously reported in the ranges 3.59-8.09 mg.g⁻¹ and 1.18-3.59 mg.g⁻¹, respectively, in freeze-
386 dried SCG from *Robusta* and *Arabica* varieties. The extraction procedure involved the drying of
387 the SCG, the defatting with petroleum ether (1:11, w/v) for 3 h at 60 °C in a Soxhlet extraction
388 system, the extraction of the SCG residue with water at 90 °C for 6 min (16 mL/g SCG) and the
389 freeze-drying of the extract [38], which is not cost-effective for SCG valorization. The
390 concentration for both caffeine and 5-CGA obtained by the SUPRAS-based extraction were
391 similar to those previously reported for the drip filter method [38] taking into account that actual
392 concentrations will be influenced by coffee variety and roasting degree [39].

393
394 Since the optimization was done on the basis of caffeine and 5-CGA only, optimal SUPRAS
395 extracts were further analysed by LC-MS/MS to confirm the presence of common bioactives
396 expected in SCG (alkaloids, phenolic compounds and niacin) [40]. Abundant MS peaks
397 corresponding to *n*-O-dicaffeoyl quinic acids, *n*-O-feruloylquinic acids, *n*-O-caffeoylquinic
398 acids, *n*-O-feruloylquinic lactones, *n*-O-coumaroylquinic acids, *n*-O-caffeoylshikimic acid, *n*-O-
399 caffeoylquinic lactones, caffeine, niacin, trigonelline and N-methylpyridinium were obtained

400 (Table 1). Fig. 4 A and B shows the MRM chromatograms recorded in negative and positive
401 acquisition modes (only the most abundant isomer of the main classes are labelled).

402

403 *3.2. Functional and microbiological properties of SUPRAS extracts*

404

405 3.2.1. Total phenolic content (TPC)

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407 Phenolic compounds are the main contributors to the strong antioxidant activity of coffee brews
408 and processing by-products [39]. The use of HPLC measurements instead of the standard Folin-
409 Ciocalteu assay has been recommended by different authors to avoid overestimation due to the
410 presence of reducing sugars, proteins and ascorbic acids, among others [41,42]. As mentioned
411 before, different isomeric peaks of the major groups of polyphenolic compounds present in SCG
412 were identified, namely *n*-O-dicaffeoyl quinic acids (n=4), *n*-O-feruloylquinic acids (n=4), *n*-O-
413 caffeoylquinic acids (n=4, being 5-CGA the most abundant), *n*-O-feruloylquinic lactones (n=5),
414 *n*-O-coumaroylquinic acids (n=2), *n*-O-caffeoylshikimic acid (n=2) and *n*-O-caffeoylquinic
415 lactones (n=2) . Their concentration were estimated by external calibration against 5-CGA due to
416 the lack of authentic standards for all of them.

417

418 The TPC obtained with the SUPRAS extraction at optimal conditions (see section 3.1) was 14,4
419 \pm 0.5 mg CGA/ g wet SCG (equivalent to 60.1 mg CGA per mg of extracted dry SCG). This
420 value was near the TPC reported for USAE (71.7 mg CAE/g SCG, extraction for 2 h at room
421 temperature and ethanol/solid ratio of 30) [20], that is, for the best of our knowledge, the highest
422 reported for SCG. The high extraction efficiency of SUPRAS for phenolic compounds, the wide
423 variety of phenolics extracted (see Table 1 and Figure 4), and the fact that samples were
424 immediately processed, without further treatment, could account for the high TPC value found in
425 our experiments. Values for SUPRAS were higher than those reported for conventional SLE (16-
426 18 mg GAE/g) [18–20], SFE (~4 mg CAE/g) [20] or Soxhlet (18-22 mg CAE/g). However, it is
427 known that TPC values depend on variables such as the roasting process [43], the preparation
428 method (grinding degree or particle size, coffee:water ratio, water temperature, extraction time,
429 etc.) and the technique followed for TPC estimation too, so that these factors can also influence
430 results and differences between reported levels. Some advantages of SUPRAS were the low

431 solvent/solid ratio (11.7 mL/g dry SCG) and the fact that the extraction was done at room
432 temperature during 1 min.

433

434 3.2.2. Antioxidant activity

435

436 SUPRAS extracts, rich in TPC, were further tested for antioxidant activity using three assays
437 (see section 2.8). The maximum value for the antioxidant capacity (100%) means that the
438 respective reagent was reduced by the effect of the antioxidants present in the SUPRAS extract.
439 The antioxidant capacity with DPPH (4.1 mg SUPRAS extract/mL) and FRAP (2.5 mg SUPRAS
440 extract/mL) was $21 \pm 3\%$ and $68 \pm 4\%$, respectively. Values of DPPH antioxidant capacity have
441 been reported in the range 14.4-93.5% in extracts from dry SCG, with those techniques
442 enhancing TPC extraction too, such as Soxhlet, USAE and MAE (EC_{50} concentration values in
443 the range 0.2-1 mg extract/mL). [20,23] The same Soxhlet and USAE extracts gave values in the
444 range 160-381 μM TEAC/g extract. [20], while for SUPRAS a value of $405 \pm 6 \mu\text{M}$ TEAC/g
445 extract was measured. These results are in line with their high TPC content.

446

447 3.2.3. Antimicrobial activity

448

449 Previous studies have reported that phenolic substances, alkaloids and melanoidins present in the
450 coffee have antibacterial activity [13]. However, even though the antimicrobial activity of coffee
451 by-products can be attributed to any of their compounds, some studies suggest that bacteria are
452 highly sensitive to phenolic acids [44], while other authors report that caffeine is the cause for
453 the inhibition of growth in gram-negative bacteria, and that chlorogenic acid is less efficient
454 against *S. enterica* [45].

455

456 The antimicrobial activity of SUPRAS was tested against *P. putida*, *S. enterica*, *S. aureus* and *B.*
457 *cereus*. Both *P. putida* and *S. enterica* have the ability to form biofilms [46], which is a strategy
458 developed by bacteria to protect themselves from harmful substances such as antibiotics. For this
459 reason, multiple studies are conducted to control these microorganisms in food. *S. aureus*, can
460 produce different infections such pneumonia [47]. Respect to *B. cereus*, it has been reported to
461 produce five enterotoxins and one emetic toxin and their spores are resistant to many processes

462 as low and high temperatures, desiccation, disinfectant agents, ionization, radiation and
463 ultraviolet light [48]. *A priori*, the complex mixture of compounds that could be present in
464 SUPRAS extracts from SCG, could be used for enhancing functional properties such as
465 antimicrobial activity to be used in the food industry as a preservative, extending the shelf life of
466 food, or even in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic sector.

467
468 The minimum inhibitory capacity (MIC), considered as the lowest concentration of SUPRAS
469 extract that inhibited the growth of the microorganism tested (two gram-positive and two-gram
470 negative bacteria), were calculated. SUPRAS extracts showed antimicrobial activities toward the
471 growth of the target bacteria at varying degrees of concentrations. Thus, gram-positive bacteria
472 (*B. cereus*, *S. aureus*) were found more resistant, with a MIC value of 287 mg SUPRAS
473 extract/mL. On the contrary, gram-negative bacteria (*S. enterica*, *P. putida*) were very sensitive
474 with a MIC value of 2.87 mg SUPRAS extract/mL.

475
476 The literature reporting the antibacterial capacity of coffee waste is very scarce. Values ranged
477 between 5 and 60 mg extract/mL for SCG extracted with subcritical water [21]. In this study,
478 gram-positive (*B. cereus*, *S. aureus*) and gram-negative (*E. Coli*, *S. typhi*) bacteria were tested
479 with methods involving different modifiers and pretreatments. MIC values were in the ranges 20-
480 40 mg extract/mL for *B. cereus*, 5 mg extract/mL for *S. aureus*, 10-20 mg extract /mL for *E. Coli*
481 and 20-60 mg extract/mL for *S. typhi*.

482 483 **4. Conclusions**

484
485 This study shows the first insights on the potential of SUPRAS, nanostructured solvents made up
486 of assembled amphiphile aggregates, for valorization of coffee waste. Results proved that these
487 solvents offer good extraction capacity of high-added value compounds from coffee by-products
488 with interest for the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry. Furthermore, extracts showed
489 antioxidant capacity and antimicrobial effects to gram-negative bacteria. SUPRAS extraction
490 offer rapid, simple and low cost methods and could be directly applied to the extraction of
491 bioactives from wet by-products. Given the high number of biocompatible amphiphiles
492 commercially available, the use of SUPRAS for agrifood by-product valorization is promising.

493

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499

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648

649 **Figure captions**

650

651 **Figure 1.** Schematic picture of SUPRAS production and SUPRAS-based extraction of SCGs

652

653 **Figure 2.** Extraction rate of caffeine (average of three replicates, relative standard deviation,
654 RSD: 5-10%) from SCG with SUPRAS synthesized under different percentages of organic
655 solvent (% v/v ethanol or THF) and amphiphiles (% v/v hexanol or decanoic acid). The optimal
656 conditions are shown in a different color.

657

658 **Figure 3.** Extraction rate of 5-CGA (average of three replicates, RSD: 5-10%) from SCG with
659 SUPRAS synthesized under different percentages of organic solvent (% v/v ethanol or THF) and
660 amphiphiles (% v/v hexanol or decanoic acid). The optimal conditions are shown in a different
661 color.

662

663 **Figure 4.** LC-(ESI) MS-MS peaks corresponding to the extracted ion chromatograms of *n-O*-
664 dicaffeoyl quinic acids, *n-O*-feruloylquinic acids (*n*-FQA), *n-O*-caffeoylquinic acids (*n*-CQA), *n*-
665 *O*-feruloylquinic lactones (*n*-FQL), *n-O*-coumaroylquinic acids (*n*-CSA), *n-O*-caffeoylshikimic
666 acid, *n-O*-caffeoylquinic lactones (*n*-CQL), caffeine (C), niacin (N), trigonelline (T) and N-
667 methylpyridinium (Table 1). Fig. A and B shows the MRM chromatograms recorded in negative
668 and positive acquisition modes, respectively. Only the most intense isomers of the most abundant
669 classes are labelled.

670

Table 1. Polyphenolic compounds, alkaloids and niacin identified in SUPRAS extracts, two main fragments were monitored for each class according reference [40]

Compound class	Abbreviation	Parent ion	Fragment 1	Fragment 2	Retention times	^a Area (sum of peaks)	Polarity
<i>n</i> -O-Dicaffeoylquinic acids	n-DCQAs	515	179	135	31.1, 31.8, 32.4, 35.2	43804	-
<i>n</i> -O-Feruloylquinic acids	n-FQAs	367	193	191	17.3, 18.4, 22.8, 23.7	118109	-
<i>n</i> -O-Caffeoylquinic acids	n-CQAs	353	191	173	13.0, 16.1, 17.7, 18.5	220745	-
<i>n</i> -O-Feruloylquinic lactones	n-FQLs	349	175	193	26.8, 28.9, 30.3, 30.9, 32.8	829621	-
<i>n</i> -O-Coumaroylquinic acids	n-CouQAs	337	191	173	21.8, 22.2	5273	-
<i>n</i> -O-caffeoylshikimic acid	n-CSAs	335	179	173	20.6, 23.8	152796	-
<i>n</i> -O-caffeoylquinic lactones	n-CQLs	335	135	161	25.3, 26.4	1157812	-
Trigonelline	T	138	92	94	2.2	52738	+
Niacin	N	124	106	80	3.2	4776	+
Caffeine	C	195	138		17.8	14961897	+

^aThe most abundant fragment was used for quantifying each peak

Fig.1

Fig. 2

(A) SUPRAS Hexanol-THF-water

(B) SUPRAS Hexanol-EtOH-water

(C) SUPRAS Decanoic Acid-THF-water

(D) SUPRAS Decanoic Acid-EtOH

Fig. 3

Fig.4